

PHONETIC AND LEXICAL FEATURES OF BORROWED WORDS IN CHINESE

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Abstract. *The given article dwells on issues concerning the study of phonetic and lexical features of borrowed words in Chinese. It is worth stressing that it is far from the generally accepted practice. On the contrary, it is an element of the subculture of certain youth groups, but it has the right to exist and walk in certain and rather small circles.*

It is concluded that the position of foreign languages in modern world, its position in China and a very wide range of English words derived from Chinese, we can confidently express our own idea that all of these are used both in everyday language and in colloquial one.

Keywords: *phonetic and lexical features, borrowing, borrowed words, Chinese language, position of foreign languages.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola xitoy tilidagi o'zlashtirilgan so'zlarning fonetik va leksik xususiyatlarini o'rganishga oid masalalarga to'xtalib o'tadi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bu umumiy qabul qilingan amaliyotdan uzoqdir. Aksincha, bu ma'lum yoshlar guruhlari submadaniyatining elementidir, lekin u muayyan va juda kichik doiralarda mavjud bo'lish va yurish huquqiga ega.*

Xorijiy tillarning zamonaviy dunyoda tutgan o'rni, Xitoydagi o'rni va xitoy tilidan olingan inglizcha so'zlarning juda keng assortimenti, bularning barchasi kundalik tilda ham, so'zlashuv nutqida ham qo'llanishi haqida o'z fikrimizni ishonch bilan ifodalashimiz mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *fonetik va leksik xususiyatlar, o'zlashuv, o'zlashtirilgan so'zlar, xitoy tili, xorijiy tillarning o'rni.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы изучения фонетических и лексических особенностей заимствованных слов китайского языка. Стоит подчеркнуть, что это далеко от общепринятой практики. Наоборот, это элемент субкультуры определенных молодежных групп, но он имеет право на существование и хождение в определенных и достаточно узких кругах.*

Сделан вывод о том, что положение иностранных языков в современном мире, его положение в Китае и весьма широкий спектр английских слов, происходящих от китайского, позволяют с уверенностью выразить собственную мысль о том, что все они используются как в повседневном языке, так и в разговорном.

Ключевые слова: *фонетические и лексические особенности, заимствование, заимствованные слова, китайский язык, положение иностранных языков.*

Introduction

It is common-knowledge that the term vowel in Chinese is 外来词 wàiláicí, that is, words that borrowed from other language; another version of it is 外来语 wàiláiyǔ - to introduce the material of a foreign language into one's own language, it is usually understood as the etymological meaning of Chinese, which has the same meaning as the word of another language, partially or completely preserving the phonetic state of a foreign word and to one degree or another "Sinification" in its full meaning can be used as literal words in certain cases [1, p.4].

The effectiveness aspect of the relevant process depends more on the writer characteristics, that the use of Chinese borrowings in English literary speech is closely related, first of all, to the

fundamental difference of writing systems. Chinese, which acts as the receiving language of borrowings, because the alphabetic system is based on Latin letters [2; 3].

At the same time, Chinese as a language is characterized by an ideographic type of script, and modern Chinese hieroglyphic script is based on ideograms, so the graphic acquisition of Chinese borrowing poses certain problems.

The objective of the corpus of our study is to dwell on phonetic and lexical peculiarities of borrowed words in Chinese in terms of its function.

Methodology

While canvassing phonetic and lexical peculiarities of borrowed words in Chinese, we have resorted to the following visual methods, such as: comparative and historical, synchronic and diachronic ones.

Main results and dissuasion

In Chinese, there are no inflections and auxiliary morphemes (prefixes and suffixes), therefore, when entering the Chinese language system, any grammatical forms are replaced by separate words, which, although they can add a series of more complex units, but the real elements are not inflectional.

Upon the whole, word-building (including the transformation of the grammatical meaning of the lexical elements of the language in order to analytically express the category of time, logical connections with other units within the phrase/sentence, etc.) is not determined by the addition of clauses, as well as individual syllables, because the relevant case in the system of Chinese (agglutination) occurs, but it takes place through the addition of lexical units characterized by the unity of meaning and it follows that for Chinese in comparison with English, in which there are also affixation and non-affixation ways of word-building, which is a productive way of word-combination in Chinese, the difference between the systems of the original language and the recipient language is of great significance.

It is worth mentioning that honetic transcription peculiarities are important in Chinese. Among all types of borrowed words, despite the issues beset with the transmission of pronunciation, the vowel form is the most common. For native Chinese languages, each syllable marked with a hieroglyph is not only a phonetic unit, but a semantic unit either.

Hereby, we decided to carry out and adduce some appropriate examples of phonetic adaptation of borrowed English words in Chinese.

For example, the word *coffee* can be a clear example of phonetic borrowing in Chinese - the word in question is transmitted through the Chinese phonetic characters 咖 *kā* and 啡 *fei*, which are similar in sound only and have no semantic meaning.

It should be noted that the word *cocoa* is translated as 可可 *kěkě*.

The hieroglyph that made it has its own meaning:

1. to be strong;
2. permitted;
3. the meaning is not related to this drink.

In 1920-1940-ies, *Coca-Cola* was produced in bottles with the English inscription *Coca-Cola*. With the spread in the Chinese market in the late 70-ies, the Americans decided to translate the name of beverage into Chinese, but they could not, because in Chinese, every foreign word is written in Chinese characters, and every character has its own meaning [4, p.400].

Thus, by printing the labels with the hieroglyphs *kekun kela*, it became clear that the relevant phrase has the same meaning as *a wax-filled snake*, they made an endeavor to translate it as *keku kela* - it turned out to be better: *the wax lizard bites*. As a result, we managed to find a very successful *kěkǒukělè 可口可乐*, which can be said to caress the mouth, caress the soul [5, p. 40], more precisely, *it is fresh, it can be enjoyed, or it is delicious and funny, interesting*.

Moreover, in Chinese, there is a series of derived words that are more similar to such terms:
- the name of alcoholic beverages *威士忌 wēishìjǐ - whiskey*, *白兰地 báilándì - cognac*.

Neither hieroglyph has anything to do with alcohol, but is used only for onomatopoeia. The following words belong to the same borrowing category: *克兰姆 kèlánmǔ - gram*, *克菲尔 kèfēiěr - kefir*, *卡拉特 kǎlātè - karate*, *披萨 pīsà - pizza*, *批萨 pīsà - pizza*, *批萨-克菲尔 kèfēiěr - in 克菲尔 kèfēiěr hiangbo - shampoo*, *阿司匹林 āsīpīlín - aspirin*, *比基尼 bǐjīní - bikini*, *模特儿 móter - model*, *瑜伽 yújiā - yoga*, *普拉提 pūlātí - pilates*, etc.

Into the bargain, one of the main ways of borrowing is tracking, which is widely resorted to in the field of the edition of Chinese special dictionary. When a foreign word or phrase is borrowed, it is divided into semantic parts, then these parts of lexicons are more or less correctly translated into Chinese, keeping the structure of the word formation.

The following lexical types are derived from European languages by tracing from their languages: *高峰时间 gāofēng shíjiān high hours*; *速溶茶 sù róng chá instant tea*; *冰棒 bīngbàng popsicle, where 冰 is ice, ice cream and 棒 is stick, stick*.

Extensive computerization of English paper was brought to China: *网吧 wǎngbā - Internet bar (Internet cafe)*; *网虫 wǎngchóng - internet friend*; *网虫 wǎngchóng - Internet worm - a lover of staying on the Internet*.

Some trace terms came to China with western parts of modern clothing: *库娃 kùwà - tight, literally - like a combination of pants and socks*; *牛仔裤 niúzǎikù - jeans, literally trousers for shepherds (cowboys)*.

In order to make Chinese more understandable, it is important to include them in separate lexico-grammatical categories of words. This is manifested in the addition of similar and more complex words to the borrowed ones, defining their general notions. A single or complex word has a classifying feature, namely, it indicates to which group or class of concepts it belongs [6, p.100].

As a result of such a combination, hybrid words are obtained, for example: *motorcycle*; *trolleybus, which is 车 wagon, cart*; *吉普车 jí pǔ chē "jeep"*; *芭蕾舞 bālěiwǔ "ballet", which 舞 means to dance, to step*;

An understudied phenomenon of Chinese that is common among young people in electronic correspondence (email, SMS, Skype) is the use of identical consonants in Chinese numbers and quotation marks. For example:

39	Thank You
505	SOS

881

拜拜唉 – Bye-Bye!

It is worth stressing that it is far from the generally accepted practice. On the contrary, it is an element of the subculture of certain youth groups, but it has the right to exist and walk in certain and rather small circles.

Conclusion

Adducing and analyzing the position of foreign languages in modern world, its position in China and a very wide range of English words derived from Chinese, we can confidently express our own idea that all of these are used both in everyday language and in colloquial one.

REFERENCES

1. Wang Liao-i. (1954) Basics of Chinese grammar / Wang Liao-i. Lane from China language G. N. Raiskaya, ed. A. A. Dragunov and Zhou Song-Yuan. - M.: Foreign Literature Publishing House, - 262 p.
2. Chu Peizhu, Jin Nailu. (2016) A textbook on the Chinese language: counting words. – M.: Chance, – 216 p.
3. Shi Yuwei. (2003) Foreign borrowings in Chinese. - Beijing: Shan'u Yinshuguan Publishing House, - 239 pp..
4. Shi Yuwei. (2019) Xinhua Dictionary of Loanwords. - Beijing: Shanwu Yinshuguan Publishing House, - 1604 p.
5. Shchichko V.F. (2004) Theory and practice of translation: textbook. - M.: Vostok-Zapad. - 223 p.
6. Yang Xipeng. (2007) Learning Chinese foreign words. - Shanghai: Shanghai People's Publishing House, - 295 p.